

EFFECT OF STACKING SEQUENCE ON STRENGTH AND FAILURE PROCESS IN QUASI-ISOTROPIC CFRP LAMINATES WITH TOUGHENED INTERLAMINAR LAYERS

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SUMMARY: Effects of stacking sequences on the strength and microscopic failure processes in quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates under static tensile loading are investigated. Observation of microscopic failure process is conducted by using an optical microscope and a X-ray radiography. The material system used is a CFRP with a toughened interlaminar layer at every ply interface. The stacking sequences are $(0/45/90/-45)_s$ and $(45/0/-45/90)_s$. By the edge observation of the plain specimens, transverse crack density is measured as a function of laminate stress. By the X-ray radiography observation, delamination onset and growth is detected. To discuss the transverse cracking, a modeling based on damage mechanics analysis is conducted. To explain delamination behavior, a simple energy release rate analysis is conducted.

KEYWORDS: delamination, energy release rate, interlaminar layer, microscopic failure process, quasi-isotropic laminates, strength, transverse crack, X-ray radiography

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are used in the form of multidirectional laminates. Failure process in CFRP laminates involves unique damages, such as, transverse cracks and delamination. It is very important to understand the behavior of these microscopic damages.

O'Brien [1] conducted static and fatigue tensile tests on quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates. Delamination onset and growth were observed by X-ray radiography. He derived the energy release rate associated with free-edge delamination by using the classical lamination theory.

Masters and Reifsnider [2] observed multiplication of transverse cracks in quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates under tensile loading by using the replica technique. It was found that the transverse crack density saturates before the final fracture of the laminates. They explained the saturated crack density by using the shear-lag analysis.

As listed above, the experimental observations of damage progress in quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates have been conducted, but the modeling of damage progress is not well established.

On the other hand, it is pointed out that CFRP has low interlaminar fracture toughness. To overcome this problem, some methods to toughen laminates are suggested. One of them is to utilize good processability of thermoset resin and high fracture toughness of thermoplastic resin. This hybridization of thermoset and thermoplastic resins is achieved by dispersing particulate thermoplastic resin into thermoset base resin. One example of these material systems is T800H/3900-2 which is used in the present study [3, 4].

The effectiveness of employment of the interlaminar layers to enhance the interlaminar fracture toughness is proved [3, 4], but the mechanical behavior of their laminates is not well understood including microscopic failure process. In the present study, effects of stacking sequences on the strength and microscopic failure processes in quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with toughened interlaminar layers under tensile loading are investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

A material system used is interlaminar toughened carbon/epoxy T800H/3900-2 laminates in which polyamide particle-dispersed epoxy matrix layers are placed between each layer. The T800H/3900-2 prepreg system has tough and fine polyamide particles on its surfaces, which results in formation of the interlaminar-toughened layers at every ply interface in the laminates. The thickness of the interlaminar-toughened layers is about 30 μ m. The laminate configurations are quasi-isotropic $(0/45/90/-45)_S$ and $(45/0/-45/90)_S$. The fiber volume fraction is about 55 %. The specimen size is 150 mm long and 25 mm wide. GFRP tabs are glued on the specimens which results in specimen gage length of 90 mm.

Damage Observation

Quasi-static tensile tests are performed at room temperature. The crosshead speed is 0.5mm/min. By the observation of polished specimen edge, damage progress is measured as a function of laminate strain. During the tests, the testing machine is periodically stopped, and the specimen edge is observed by an optical microscope. Observed area is 50 mm long at the center of the specimen. The number of transverse cracks in each ply is counted to obtain the transverse crack density, which is defined as the number of transverse cracks per unit length.

The specimens are also observed by a X-ray radiography. By the X-ray radiography, delamination onset and growth are detected. Iodozinc (ZnI), a dye penetrant opaque to X-rays, is applied along the specimen edge. Specimens are exposed to X-rays for 150 s at 20 kV and 2 mA. A X-ray point-source unit positioned 570 mm away from the specimen is used.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the mechanical properties of T800H/3900-2 quasi-isotropic laminates. Figure 1 shows typical stress-strain curves and damage progress in the laminates. Large effect of stacking sequence is seen in tensile strength, that is, tensile strength of $(0/45/90/-45)_S$ laminate is higher than that of $(45/0/-45/90)_S$ laminate. It should be noticed that Young's modulus and failure strain are very similar. In stress-strain curves of $(45/0/-45/90)_S$ laminate, more knee points or discontinuous points are observed than in those of $(0/45/90/-45)_S$ laminates, which may be due to occurrences of severe damages.

Figure 2 shows edge damage state observed by an optical microscope in (a) $(0/45/90/-45)_S$ at $\sigma = 785\text{MPa}$ where σ is laminate stress, (b) $(45/0/-45/90)_S$ at $\sigma = 550\text{MPa}$ and (c) $(45/0/-45/90)_S$ at $\sigma = 733\text{MPa}$. Figure 3 shows transverse crack density as a function of laminate strain in (a) $(0/45/90/-45)_S$ and (b) $(45/0/-45/90)_S$ laminates.

In $(0/45/90/-45)_S$ laminates, the first microscopic damage observed is a transverse crack in 90° ply. At higher strain levels, transverse cracks in 45° and -45° plies are observed. As the laminate strain increases, the number of transverse cracks in each ply increases. The transverse cracks in 45° ply run through the thickness of two adjacent -45° plies at the center of the laminate. The transverse crack density in 90° ply is much higher than those in 45° and -45° plies. The transverse crack density in -45° ply is slightly higher than that in 45° ply. In this laminate configuration, delamination is not observed in the failure process.

In $(45/0/-45/90)_S$ laminates, the transverse cracks in 90° ply and free-edge delamination at $-45/90$ interface are observed at similar strain level. At higher strain levels, transverse cracks in -45° ply are observed, but not in 45° ply. In 45° ply, surface damage as shown in Fig.2 (b) is observed. Delamination in 90° ply is also observed.

Figure 4 shows X-radiographs of T800H/3900-2 $(45/0/-45/90)_S$ ((a) $\sigma=452\text{MPa}$, (b) $\sigma=517\text{MPa}$, (c) $\sigma=581\text{MPa}$, (d) $\sigma=646\text{MPa}$, (e) $\sigma=711\text{MPa}$). Delamination growth in the laminate width direction and transverse crack multiplication is clearly observed.

DISCUSSION

Transverse Cracking

To explain the difference in transverse cracking due to the difference in stacking sequence, micromechanical modeling is conducted. In the present study, the energy release rate associated transverse crack formation is considered.

Gudmundson and Zang [5] developed an analytical model for the prediction of the thermoelastic properties of composite laminates containing transverse cracks. The in-plane compliance matrix of laminates with transverse cracks, $S_{II(c)}$, can be expressed using in-plane compliance matrix without transverse cracks, S_{II} , as

$$S_{II(c)} = \left((S_{II})^{-1} - \sum_{k=1}^N v^k \rho^k (A^k)^T \sum_{i=1}^N \beta^{ki} A^i \right)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where v : volume fraction of ply k , ρ : normalized crack density in ply k , A : matrix defined by compliance matrix of each ply and unit normal vector on the crack surface, β : matrix associated with average crack opening displacement. In the present study, the energy release rate associated with transverse crack formation is derived.

Assuming that transverse cracks occur at a constant load and that they occur at the midway between the existing transverse cracks, the energy release rate when the transverse crack density becomes 2ρ from ρ , $G_t(2\rho)$ at laminate stress σ is expressed as

$$G(2\rho) = \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{E(2\rho)} - \frac{1}{E(\rho)} \right) \frac{h}{\rho t} \quad (2)$$

where $E(2\rho)$ and $E(\rho)$: Young's modulus of the laminate in which the transverse crack density is 2ρ and ρ , respectively, h : the laminate thickness and t : the cracking ply thickness. Young's modulus of the laminate is obtained by using eq.(1) as a function of the transverse crack density. In the present study, normalized energy release rate associated with transverse cracking, G_m , when $\rho \rightarrow 0$ defined as

$$G_m = \lim_{\rho \rightarrow 0} \frac{G(2\rho)}{\sigma^2} \quad (3)$$

is calculated. Material properties used in the analysis are listed in Table 2.

Table 3 shows the normalized energy release rate associated with transverse cracking in each ply. In $(0/45/90/-45)_s$ laminate, the energy release rate in -45° ply is higher than in 45° ply, which corresponds to the results that transverse crack density is higher in -45° ply than in 45° ply. In $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ laminate, the energy release rate in 45° ply is very small which is consistent with the experimental result that transverse crack is not observed. In 45° ply, the surface damage is observed instead of transverse cracks as shown in Fig.2 (b). In both laminates, the energy release rate in 90° ply is relatively small though many transverse cracks are observed. This implies that the critical energy release rate in 90° ply is smaller than that in 45° (or -45°) ply. The analysis will be a basis for a quantitative estimation of transverse crack density.

Delamination

O'Brien [1] derived an equation for the energy release rate associated with straight-edge delamination growth, G_d , as

$$G_d = \frac{\varepsilon^2 h}{2m} (E_{LAM} - E^*) \quad (4)$$

where ε : the nominal strain, m : the number of delaminations formed and E_{LAM} and E^* : the laminate modulus before and after delamination. In the present study, normalized energy release rate associated with delamination growth, G_{dn} , defined as

$$G_{dn} = \frac{G_d}{\varepsilon^2 h} \quad (5)$$

is calculated. Material properties used in the analysis are listed in Table 2. Table 4 shows the normalized energy release rate associated with delamination growth at each ply interface. It is found that the energy release rate at -45/90 interface at which delamination was observed is much higher than that at other interfaces. This implies that this analysis is useful to predict delamination location.

CONCLUSION

Tensile tests are conducted on quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates with toughened interlaminar layers. Effects of stacking sequences on the strength and microscopic failure processes are investigated. Observation of microscopic failure process is conducted by using an optical microscope and a X-ray radiography. To explain the difference in microscopic failure process due to the difference in stacking sequence, micromechanical modeling of damage onset and growth is conducted. Micromechanical modeling based on the precise observation of microscopic failure process will be a basis for damage tolerance design.

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Table 1. Mechanical properties of T800H/3900-2 quasi-isotropic laminates.

Laminates	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Failure Strain (%)
(0/45/90/-45) _S	52.8	799	1.48
(45/0/-45/90) _S	53.4	744	1.49

Table 2. Material properties used in the analyses.

Material System T800H/3900-2	
Longitudinal Young's modulus, E_1 (GPa)	143
Transverse Young's modulus, E_2 (GPa)	7.99
In-plane shear modulus, G_{12} (GPa)	3.96
Longitudinal Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}	0.345
Transverse Poisson's ratio, ν_{23}	0.490

Table 3. Normalized energy release rate associated with transverse cracking.

Laminates	Cracking ply	Normalized energy release rate [$\times 10^{-17} \text{ N}^{-1} \text{ m}^3$]
(0/45/90/-45) _S	45° ply	22.7
	90° ply	3.28
	-45° ply	45.4
(45/0/-45/90) _S	45° ply	11.2
	-45° ply	22.7
	90° ply	6.54

Table 4. Normalized energy release rate associated with delamination growth.

Laminates	Delamination Interface	Normalized energy release rate [GPa]
(0/45/90/-45) _S	0/45	0.000323
	45/90	0.733
	90/-45	0.818
(45/0/-45/90) _S	45/0	0.818
	0/-45	0.733
	-45/90	2.05*

* Delamination is observed.

Figure 1: Typical stress-strain curves and damage progress in T800H/3900-2 quasi-isotropic laminates. (a) $(0/45/90/-45)_s$ (b) $(45/0/-45/90)_s$

Figure 2: Edge damage state observed by an optical microscope in (a) $(0/45/90/-45)_s$ at $\sigma = 785 \text{ MPa}$, (b) $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ at $\sigma = 550 \text{ MPa}$ and (c) $(45/0/-45/90)_s$, $\sigma = 733 \text{ MPa}$.

Figure 2: (Continued) Edge damage state observed by an optical microscope in (a) $(0/45/90-45)_s$ at $\sigma = 785\text{MPa}$, (b) $(45/0/-45/90)_s$ at $\sigma = 550\text{MPa}$ and (c) $(45/0/-45/90)_s$, $\sigma = 733\text{MPa}$.

Figure 3: Transverse crack density as a function of laminate strain in T800H/3900-2 quasi-isotropic laminates. (a) $(0/45/90-45)_s$, (b) $(45/0/-45/90)_s$

Figure 4: X-radiographs of T800H/3900-2 (45/0/-45/90)_s, (a) $\sigma = 452$ MPa (b) $\sigma = 517$ MPa, (c) $\sigma = 581$ MPa, (d) $\sigma = 646$ MPa (e) $\sigma = 711$ MPa.